

Seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (60 × 40 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm water 7 d after seeding (DAS). The boxes were covered with nylon net cages 20 DAS and 10 moth pairs/cage released in each cage. (A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung inside the cage as food for the moths.)

Moths were allowed to oviposit 3-4 d. LF damage was assessed 15 d after release of moths.

The same accessions were screened in microplots (2 × 2 m).

TNAULFR831324, 832042, 842718, 842735, and 842745 exhibited good resistance in the greenhouse and in the microplots (see table). □

Reaction of rice seedlings to LF. Coimbatore, India, 1987 wet season.

Accession	Cross	Damage rating ^a	
		Greenhouse	Microplot
TNAULFR831324	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	3
TNAULFR832042	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	5
TNAULFR842718	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	3
TNAULFR842735	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
TNAULFR842745	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
Balam (donor)	—	3	5
RP2430-350-54	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-361-3	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-372-75	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
ARC11281 (donor)	—	5	5
Choorapundy (donor)	—	5	5
TN1 (susceptible check)	DGWG/Tsai-Yuan-Chan	9	9
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	—	3	3

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Field incidence of and host resistance to Angoumois grain moth (AGM)

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We surveyed field incidence of AGM *Sitotroga cerealella* O. on rice in the field at the Agricultural College in Madurai and the Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute in Aduthurai. Seed samples of 100 g for each variety were collected in polythepe bags and adult moth emergence monitored for 6 wk.

AGM emerged from 124 of 213 samples at Madurai and from 59 of 151 samples at Aduthurai. Incidence was highest in IR and CO varieties; IR20, IR50, IR54, IR64, CO 25, CO 31, CO 37, CO 42, CO 43, CO 44, ACM11, ACM12, IET7254, ADT36, AD85003, NLR9672, Ponni, TNAU801790, TNAU831293, TNAU831520, and TNAU831521 showed field infestation in both places.

We evaluated 38 CO varieties for resistance on the basis of number of moths emerging, percentage infested grains, weight loss, and weight of adult moths; 15 were resistant.

Resistant CO 1, CO 27, and CO 32; moderately resistant CO 40; moderately susceptible CO 42; and highly

Physical and biochemical characters of rices resistant to Angoumois grain moth in India.

Variety	Husk ^a thickness (cm)	Physical characters			Biochemical factors		
		Grain hardness ^a (alkali value)	Length: breadth ratio ^b	100-grain weight ^c (g)	Silica, content ^d (%)	Total protein ^d (%)	Total amylose ^d (%)
CO 32	0.031	2	4.0	1.8	18.9	5.9	23.9
CO 21	0.037	2	3.5	2.0	19.1	9.8	28.9
CO 1	0.032	1	3.1	2.1	17.9	9.2	24.5
CO 40	0.027	4	2.0	2.3	16.8	8.2	20.7
CO 42	0.019	3	2.7	2.1	16.8	6.5	19.9
CO 43	0.017	4	2.1	1.9	15.1	6.5	19.4
CO 44	0.014	5	1.9	1.9	15.1	7.6	21.9

^aMean of 10 observations. ^bMean of 15 observations. ^cMean of 3 replications. ^dMean of 2 replications.

susceptible CO 43 and CO 44 were selected to study factors conferring resistance.

Husk thickness, grain hardness (alkali value), length-breadth ratio (grain fineness), 100-grain weight, and silica,

protein, and amylose content were analyzed. In general, resistant varieties had thick husk, low alkali value, coarse grain, higher 100-grain weight, and high silica, total protein, and total amylose content (see table). □

Excess water tolerance

Breeding for submergence tolerance

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In eastern India, rice seedlings are likely to be submerged 30-40 d after transplanting when the monsoon breaks

in mid-Jun. We studied FR13A, FR43B, and CN540, their two hybrids, and susceptible check IR20 for submergence tolerance and recovery.

Initial height and leaf and tiller number of 10-, 30-, and 40-d-old seedlings were recorded, and seedlings were submerged in either 30 or 60 cm deep water. Survival percentage, height and leaf number were taken, and

Survival and recovery of seedlings of different ages at 2 water depths. West Bengal, India.

seedlings left for 10 d more under saturated moisture to estimate recovery capacity.

Varieties differed significantly in initial height and leaf and tiller number. FR13A and FR43B were the tallest and had the most leaves in all age groups. In general, IR20 scored lowest for all characters, except it had the most tillers at 40 d old.

Highest survival of 10-d-old seedlings was in FR13A and CN716 at both flooding depths, followed by FR43B and CN717 (see figure). No IR20 plants survived the 60-cm water depth. All older seedlings of CN540 and FR43B survived.

Only CN716 showed complete recovery of younger seedlings at both water depths; 40-d-old seedlings surpassed both parents in 60 cm water. FR43B had good overall recovery at all seedling ages. No 10 d IR20 seedlings recovered; recovery otherwise increased gradually with seedling age.

Most varieties had higher elongation rates at 30 cm than at 60 cm water depth (see table). Ten-day-old CN540 seedlings had the highest elongation rate, FR43B elongated most in 30 cm and FR13A in 60 cm.

High initial height was correlated with low elongation rate in older seedlings

Elongation rate during submergence of 6 varieties at 10, 30, and 40 d old. West Bengal, India.

Variety	Elongation per d (%)					
	10 d old		30 d old		40 d old	
	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm
CN540 (Suresh)	13.1	1.8	4.1	8.9	6.2	7.4
FR13A	2.6	3.1	5.0	5.6	1.4	5.2
FR43B	13.1	-1.4	2.8	1.9	5.9	1.4
CN716 (FR13A/CN540)	4.9	0.2	6.3	6.3	12.0	6.4
CN717 (FR43B/CN540)	2.5	1.5	4.6	3.0	5.1	6.6
IR20 (susceptible check)	10.1	dead	1.5	2.4	-4.9	-2.2

(-0.60 and -0.70 at 30 cm, and -0.81 and -0.73 at 60 cm water) but not with survival. Initial leaf number was positively correlated with survival only in 40-d-old seedlings at 60 cm water depth (0.60).

The resistant varieties can be divided into two groups: FR13A type and CN540 or FR43B type. FR13A type was more resistant at the heterotrophic stage (seedling surviving on endosperm), CN540 type was more resistant at the autotrophic stage (seedling producing its food).

Screening at both seedling stages could help identify resistance donors. Development of bridge parents such as CN716 (FR13A/CN540) that combine both types of resistance should lead to the production of genotypes with better flood tolerance. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening criterion for cold tolerance at the seedling stage

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In the Yangtze valley in China, the first crop indica rice is sown in early Apr and transplanted in early May. Seedlings die when temperatures are abnormally low (6-10 °C for 5 d or longer). We investigated a screening criterion for cold tolerance at the seedling stage.